

Scoping review protocol on strategies to address health judicialization in universal Health Systems

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Competing interests: The authors have no competing interests to declare.

1. Background

The judicialization of health is a social claim on the right to access to health. It usually occurs due to gaps in public policies or failures in their application. In universal health systems, several institutions have implemented strategies to address this phenomenon. However, these strategies have not yet been mapped and systematized concerning Universal Health Systems.

2. Purpose of the scope review

A scoping review will be carried out to systematically identify and map evidence on strategies to address the judicialization of health in universal health systems.

3. Research question

The structured question based on the PCC acronym (Chart 1) is: What strategies are carried out to face the judicialization of health in universal health systems?

Chart 1: PCC structured question

P	Problem	Health judicialization
C	Concept	Strategies to face health judicialization
C	Context	Universal health systems

3. Methods

This scoping review will be carried out according to the Joanna Briggs Institute proposed methodology for carrying out systematic scope reviews (Levac et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2015). The review report will be conducted according to Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews guidelines and Meta-Analyzes extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) for the review report (Tricco et al., 2018).

3.1. Criteria to consider studies for this review

Types of studies

- Primary and secondary studies will be included, with a qualitative and quantitative approach, which investigate strategies to face the judicialization of universal health systems;
- Abstracts and presentations at scientific events, newsletters and administrative reports published on the internet will be included;
- We will include studies regardless of when they were performed or published;
- We will include published and unpublished studies in English, Portuguese and Spanish;

- We will exclude studies published in other languages due to the very short deadline for this review.

Topic of interest

- Documents referring to any type of strategy to address health judicialization in universal health systems will be included, both in health management and legal area.

Types of settings

- We will include studies that collected data in any country that has a universal health system, conducted at any institution, including private institutions.

3.2. Search methods to identify studies

- Searches will be performed in the following electronic databases: Medline (via PubMed), BVSsalud, Embase and Scopus.
- Gray literature searches will be carried out to identify government documents, theses, dissertations and abstracts published in conference proceedings eligible for this scoping review. Sources of unpublished studies and gray literature to be searched will include the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD) and Google Scholar (first 10 pages).
- Search strategies will be developed for each database. No limits on language or publication date will apply.

3.3. Selection of studies

- The selection will be carried out with the support of the free Rayyan reference management application QCRI.
- Two reviewers will independently evaluate each title and abstract of the identified records to make the selection. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or, when necessary, a third review author will be involved.
- The full texts of all papers identified as potentially relevant will be retrieved and eligibility will be assessed against inclusion and exclusion criteria. This process will be carried out by two independent reviewers. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or, when necessary, a third reviewer will be involved.
- A PRISMA flowchart will be included to present research results and the process of screening and eligibility of studies for inclusion.
- In the full-text phase will be presented a table listing excluded studies references from this review and the main reason(s) for exclusion.

3.4. Extraction of study information and graphics

- An extraction spreadsheet will be developed and tested with calibration between the researchers.
- The extraction will be performed by two reviewers independently. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus and a third reviewer will be engaged if necessary.
- When data is not available for a category, it will be indicated in the extraction sheet as '*not informed*'.

These categories will include the following:

- Study information (lead author, year of publication).
- Goals
- Study type (publication type, publication area, study type, methodological approach)
- Study participants and environments (countries in which the research was carried out, types of participants, environment(s) in which the study was carried out).
- Strategy addressed
- Results: conclusions of the study on the strategy; barriers, and facilitators
- Gaps limitations